

Effect of Zn and Ga doping on bioactivity, degradation, and antibacterial properties of borate 1393-B3 bioactive glass

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Bioactive glasses
Borate glasses
Zinc
Gallium
Antibacterial activity

ABSTRACT

Borate 1393-B3 bioactive glasses doped with ZnO or Ga₂O₃ (1, 3, and 6% mol) were produced by conventional melt quenching. All doped glasses showed in-vitro bioactivity in simulated body fluid (SBF). For the first time, the dissolution behavior of the glasses both in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and cell culture medium was investigated. The ion release rate in the cell culture medium increased compared to that in PBS solution. All tested glass compositions, including the parent 1393-B3 glass, showed antibacterial effect against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The incorporation of Zn and Ga enhanced the viability of MG-63 osteoblast-like cells compared to the base 1393-B3 glass. The results show the potential of Zn and Ga-doped borate glasses in multifunctional tissue engineering applications.

1. Introduction

Despite many successful clinical applications of silicate bioactive glasses (BGs), their therapeutic potential cannot be often fully exploited because of a low release rate of therapeutic ions and incomplete degradation. Therefore, the development of more biodegradable glasses based on other network forming oxides like phosphate and borate gains research interest [1]. Borate-based glasses and their conversion to hydroxyapatite (HA) in K₂HPO₄ solution in less than 4 days have been firstly reported by Day et al. [2], who used a composition based on 45S5 BG (45SiO₂-24.5Na₂O-24.5CaO-6P₂O₅ wt. %), but with SiO₂ replaced by B₂O₃ (45S5-3B). Unlike silicate glasses, when tested in body fluids borate glasses form HA directly on the surface of the unreacted glass without the formation of a borate-rich layer [3–5]. Moreover it was reported that borates are soluble in the body fluid and the degradation products can be eliminated by the body [6]. The absence of the initial layer offers higher rates of dissolution and bioactivity and with the structural difference, known as boron anomaly, results in lower chemical durability of borate glasses compared to the silica-based ones. Due to these properties, borate glasses have gained interest for biomedical

applications such as wound healing [7–10], bone tissue engineering [11] and as drug carriers [12]. Some of the borate-based BG compositions, known by the names Mirragen® and Dermafuse™, have received US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval and are commercially available [10,13].

BGs can also be functionalized by various therapeutic inorganic ions (TII), which can be incorporated into the glass network to modify and enhance their specific properties [14]. Several TII such as silver, magnesium, zinc, strontium, copper, gallium and boron have been studied as TII in tissue engineering applications [14–16]. Most of these studies have been performed with silicate-based glasses and their effects are well-known. In fact, in designing ion-releasing bioactive glasses, a major challenge is to match their dissolution rate with that of tissue healing and regeneration and the local concentration of ions, without inducing any toxic effect. Thus, reactivity, solubility, and ionic release rates need to be controlled and tailored for the desired application. Despite the interest of the scientific community, the effect of including modifying oxides on borate BG properties and the mechanisms of ion release and biological activities are still not fully understood.

The addition to BGs of TII such as gallium and zinc can contribute to

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antibacterial properties [17], enhance haemostatic ability [18] and improve vascularization. Zinc plays an important role in maintaining cell wall stability, DNA, RNA and protein synthesis and it encourages the proliferation of fibroblasts in the wound healing process [19,20]. Moreover, Zn can participate in the regulation of thrombotic factors and enhances the coagulation ability showing haemostatic properties [21, 22]. In addition to these features, zinc is an efficient antimicrobial agent [14,23], due to its inhibitory effects on several metabolic activities such as metabolized carbohydrates (glycolysis), acid production and transmembrane proton translocation [17,24].

The semimetal element gallium is not novel in clinical applications; it is used as a diagnostic [25] and therapeutic agent in cancer treatment [26]. Nowadays, different biological properties of gallium have been investigated and highlighted, such as promotion of osteogenesis and antibacterial activity. The antibacterial properties of gallium are attributed to its similarity to iron at the level of nuclear radius, ionization potential and coordination chemistry [27]. The bacteria are therefore not able to differentiate between gallium and iron [28]. Ga can thus interact with cellular processes and proteins which involve iron metabolism. Unlike iron, gallium is stable in the (III) oxidation state and it cannot take part in redox reactions under physiological conditions [29]. In this case, it cannot bond and transport oxygen within the cell, eventually poisoning the bacteria. Besides, it has been proposed that gallium promotes the haemostasis process via intrinsic coagulation pathways [18].

Zinc and/or gallium-doped borate glasses have been prepared by conventional melt-quenching [30]. Yazdi et al. [31] produced zinc (15 wt %) and gallium (2.5–15 wt %)–doped borate glasses (B_2O_3 –ZnO– Na_2O –CaO– P_2O_5), replacing boron with the dopants. In borate glass systems, both gallium and zinc play an intermediate role. The substitution of network former with intermediate ions changes the network connectivity, alters bioactivity, ion release and dissolution of the glass [1]. Deliormanlı et al. [32] added 1 and 5 wt% gallium into 1393-B3 glass. In this case, the doping elements were added to replace calcium [32]. Gallium addition altered the structure of glass significantly considering the 3 times higher molecular weight of Ga_2O_3 compared to CaO. The biological responses such as cell proliferation, mineralization and gene expression were also different since the ionic dissolution rate can affect cell cultures due to structural changes.

Yazdi et al. [30] reported that the increase of gallium content in a borate glass induced an inhibitory effect on Gram negative bacteria strains, while no such trend was observed for Gram positive bacteria. The antibacterial effect of a composite of the gallium-doped BG in poly (octanedial citrate) was also studied, showing dose-dependent behavior; the antibacterial activity increased with the amount of glass in the composite. The effect was attributed to the pH change induced by the release of ions from the BG in the scaffold [33].

The haemostatic activity of gallium has been examined by comparing chitosan/Ga doped bioactive glass composites to a commercial product (Celox™ rapid gauze). The scaffold that contains 50 wt % of gallium doped mesoporous BG showed superior properties over the Celox™ material in enhancing haemostasis with improved thrombus formation, enhanced platelet adhesion, and faster clotting rate [34].

Although the therapeutic potential of zinc and gallium is well known, their effect on bioactive response and especially ionic dissolution behavior of 1393-B3 borate glass remains to be investigated. Therefore, in this study, 1393-B3 borate BG doped with gallium or zinc (1, 3, and 6 mol %) have been produced by a melt-quenching method, substituting calcium in the glass composition. Simulated body fluid (SBF) solution was used to investigate the acellular bioactivity of the glasses. Since ionic dissolution products and their rates determine the therapeutic potential of bioactive glasses, the dissolution behavior and ion release profile of the prepared borate glass compositions were studied in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and cell culture medium (DMEM) comparatively to obtain a more realistic assessment. Moreover, the antibacterial potential of zinc and gallium addition in the borate BG was

examined against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria by broth dilution and agar diffusion methods. In parallel, the cytotoxic response of osteoblast-like cells was evaluated using extracts of the glasses in different dilution rates. The findings of this study provide a wide perspective for usage of zinc and gallium doped 1393-B3 composition in tissue engineering applications.

2. Materials and method

2.1. Preparation of the glasses

Theoretical oxide compositions of the studied glasses and their labels are given in Table 1 in mol %. In the two series ZnO or Ga_2O_3 were substituted for CaO up to 6 mol %. Adequate amounts of analytical grade precursors, including Na_2CO_3 (99,0%), K_2CO_3 (99,0%), MgO (98,0%), $CaCO_3$ (99,0%), H_3BO_3 (99,5%), ZnO (99,6%), Ga_2O_3 (99,9%), $Na_5P_3O_{10}$ (99,8%) (all CentralChem, Slovakia) were thoroughly mixed for 1 h. Then, the raw powders were melted using a PtRh10 crucible at 1150 °C for 3 h. The melt was then cast on a metal plate and subsequently annealed at 460 °C for 30 min. For further use, all glasses were crushed, ground, and sieved to different fractions depending on the used characterization techniques. For phase analysis by XRD, thermo analytical measurements, and chemical analysis by ICP-OES, the powders with particle size <100 µm were used. Particles in the range of 224–500 µm were used for the bioactivity, cytotoxicity, and antibacterial activity tests, and further characterization by FTIR and SEM tests.

2.2. Materials characterization

Phase analysis was performed on glass powder samples using X-ray diffraction (XRD, Miniflex 600 HR, Rigaku, Japan) with copper K-α radiation. The data were obtained in the 2θ range between 10 and 90°, using a 0.020° step size and dwell time of 1 s per step. The surface morphology of the glass particles was characterized via scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Auriga Base, Zeiss, Jena, Germany). DTA/TG measurements were performed in the temperature range between 35 and 1000 °C, at the heating rate of 10 °C/min, in a nitrogen atmosphere, using Netzsch STA 449 F1 Jupiter simultaneous thermal analyzer, using ~50 mg of glass powder. DTA/TG curves were evaluated by the Netzsch Proteus (version 6.0.0) software. FTIR spectra were obtained using IRAffinity-1S spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU, Japan), with 40 spectral scans in the range from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Analyzed pellets were prepared by mixing ~2 mg of glass powder with 198 mg of KBr. To determine the chemical composition of melted glasses, 25 mg of each produced glass was dissolved using microwave-assisted digestion (Speedwave 4, Berghof Products + Instruments, Germany) in an aqua regia acid mixture for inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, Agilent 5100, SVDV) measurements. The dissolved samples were diluted to 50 mL with ultrapure water before ICP-OES measurement. The method of internal standard was used to analyze with multielement standard solution containing 10 mg/L Sc and 1 mg/L Be as an internal standard. The analysis was performed in triplicate for each sample.

Table 1

Theoretical compositions of the parent and doped glasses in mol %. Labels of the glasses are also reported.

Oxide	1393-B3	1Zn	3Zn	6Zn	1Ga	3Ga	6Ga
Na ₂ O	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
K ₂ O	7.9	7.9	7.9	7.9	7.9	7.9	7.9
MgO	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7
CaO	22.1	21.1	19.1	16.1	21.1	19.1	16.1
B ₂ O ₃	54.6	54.6	54.6	54.6	54.6	54.6	54.6
P ₂ O ₅	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7
ZnO	–	1.0	3.0	6.0	–	–	–
Ga ₂ O ₃	–	–	–	–	1.0	3.0	6.0

2.3. In-vitro bioactivity

To investigate the bioactivity, the prepared glass compositions were immersed in SBF for 1 and 7 days at 37 °C. SBF (pH = 7.4) was prepared according to the protocol proposed by Kokubo et al. [35]. An amount of 75 mg of each glass powder was immersed in 50 mL SBF and placed in a shaking incubator at 37 °C and 120 rpm. The particles were rinsed with distilled water, dried at 60 °C and later analyzed by SEM and XRD after 1 day and 7 days immersion.

2.4. Ion release test in PBS and DMEM

To determine the dissolution and concentration profile of the B³⁺, Ca²⁺, Zn²⁺, P⁵⁺, Mg²⁺, and Ga³⁺ ions, immersion tests were carried out in PBS (pH: 7.4, Gibco, Germany) and DMEM (pH: 7.5, Gibco, Germany). The same protocol was followed as in the bioactivity test, with different incubation intervals set at 4 and 8 h, and 1, 2, 4, and 7 days. The dissolution media were collected and stabilized with HNO₃ to pH ~2 prior to analysis by ICP-OES (Agilent 5100 SVDV, Agilent Technologies, Inc., USA). Before the analysis, three calibration solutions were prepared to obtain a linear correlation between intensity and concentration. The stock calibration solutions were prepared from reference standards certified for ICP techniques. To avoid non-spectral interferences, a solution containing Sc (10 mg/L) and Be (1 mg/L) for internal standardization technique was prepared. The precision of the analysis for all required ions expressed as RSD % was below 5%. The measurements were made in triplicate.

2.5. Antibacterial evaluation

The antibacterial effect of the glass powders against *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) and *E. coli* (Gram-negative) bacteria were evaluated by Broth Dilution and modified Agar Disk Diffusion method [36]. Sterilization of the glass powders was performed at 160 °C for 2 h. The bacteria were grown in lysogeny broth (LB, Luria/Miller) medium at 37 °C for 24 h. Subsequently, the bacterial optical density (OD) was arranged to 0.015 (~1 × 10⁷ colony forming units/mL) at 600 nm using a spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific GENESYS 30, Germany). Glass powders were incubated in LB medium (2 g/20 mL) for 24 h by continuous shaking. After the glass separation from the LB medium by filtration, the bacterial suspension with a volume of 20 μL was added into 2 mL of the obtained elution extract. All samples were incubated at 37 °C for 4, 8 and 24 h. The relative viability of the bacteria was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{Relative bacteria viability (\%)} = \frac{OD_{\text{Sample}}}{OD_{\text{Control}}} \times 100$$

To perform the Agar Disk Diffusion method, the bacterial suspension was prepared as described above. Subsequently, LB agar was poured into Petri dishes then, 20 μL of bacterial suspension was spread on the top of agar. The pellets containing 0.2 g of bioactive glass powder were then placed on the agar and incubated for 1, 2 and 3 days at 37 °C with control groups without pellets. The pellets with a diameter of 7 mm were prepared using a hydraulic press (PE-010, Mauthe Maschinenbau) with 1 ton without any additives. The blank and control groups were prepared from LB medium and bacterial suspension in LB medium respectively. The experiments were made in triplicate. The antibacterial activity of the pellets was determined from the changes in density of the bacterial colonies in the surrounding regions. The presence and the size of these inhibition zones, defined as areas free of bacteria, were measured by digital images and subsequently analyzed with the software ImageJ [37].

2.6. In vitro cell viability assay

Human osteoblast-like cells (ECACCS, Sigma Aldrich, Darmstadt,

Germany), namely MG-63 cells, were cultured in DMEM (Gibco, Germany) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Corning, USA) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (PS, Gibco, Germany), further noted as cell culture medium (CCM), in 75 cm² cell culture flasks. The cells were grown until they reached confluency. Counted cells with trypan blue assay were seeded in 24 multi-well plates at a density of 100,000 cells/well and incubated for 24 h. The extract method was used as a biocompatibility testing methodology. In parallel, the tested glass compositions, previously sterilized as described above, were prepared as an elution extract of 10 % wt./v BG in CCM for 24 h at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. The elution extracts were separated from glass particles by filtration and diluted with the same medium at ratios of 1%, 0.1% and 0.01%. Then, the eluates were added to the cells and incubated for 48 h. Cells seeded with the same inoculum ratio and in contact with CCM and with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were used as positive and negative controls, respectively.

The cell viability was analyzed by a WST-8 assay (CCK-8, Sigma Aldrich) based on mitochondrial activity of living cells. After culturing the cells for 48 h, they were washed with PBS to remove the unattached cells and incubated with 1% WST-8 reagent in phenol red-free DMEM for 3 h. After transferring the solution into 96-well plate, the absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader (PHOMO Elisa reader, Autobio Diagnostic Co. Ltd., Zhengzhou, China). All the experiments were made in triplicate. The relative viability of the MG-63 cells was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{Cell viability (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Absorbance of sample} - \text{Absorbance of blank})}{(\text{Absorbance of positive control} - \text{Absorbance of blank})} \times 100$$

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was used for analyzing the cell morphology. After the WST-8 assay, the attached cells were washed with PBS for 15 min and subsequently fixed with a 4% w/v paraformaldehyde solution for 15 min. The plates were washed with deionized water and stained with Hematoxylin 300 μL/well for 10 min. Then, the samples were rinsed with tap water, followed by Scott's tap water (pH = 8.11) and distilled water for 5 min. An eosin solution (0.4 w/v% in a mixture of 60% ethanol and 5% acetic acid) was prepared and 400 μL eosin solution was added to each well. After 5 min the plates were washed with ethanol with purity of 95% and 99.5% respectively and dried at room temperature. The cell morphology was examined using a light microscope (Primo Vert, Carl Zeiss).

2.7. Statistical analysis

One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the differences between different samples. The significance level was set to p < 0.05. Tukey post hoc test was used for comparison of the mean values.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Glass characterization

Zn and Ga doped borate glasses were characterized by XRD analysis to verify their amorphous nature (Fig. 1). The XRD patterns revealed no detectable crystalline phases in the glass. The irregular shape of the obtained particles and fracture surfaces due to mechanical forces applied by milling are shown in Fig. 2.

Although controversial data has been reported in the literature [38], it is now generally accepted that borate glass consists of randomly arranged planar BO₃ triangles with certain fraction of six member boroxol rings [39,40] which retain the short range arrangement with bridging oxygens to interconnect the small units [41]. When other oxides are added into the system, and treated at high temperatures, different borate structures can be formed. The network of boroxol rings is interrupted, and smaller structural units are formed [41]. The addition of a small

Fig. 1. XRD diffraction patterns of Zn and Ga doped borate bioactive glasses.

amount of modifiers into borate glasses leads to formation of tetrahedral BO_4 units. With further increase of the content of modifiers the amount of BO_4 groups reaches a certain point at which the surplus cations start breaking the bridging oxygen bonds forming BO_3 units again. The amount of borate forming units then depends on the content and the type of additive ions.

The FTIR spectra of produced glasses are shown in Fig. 3. IR spectra

of borate glasses commonly show three main regions: (i) the band at $1600-1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to the superposition of the bands caused by asymmetric stretching vibrations of B–O stretching in BO_3 units [42], (ii) the band at $1200-800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ that matches the superposition of the bands from stretching vibration of BO_4 units [31] and (iii) the band at $800-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which corresponds to the $B_3\text{--}O\text{--}B_4$ bending vibrations of bridging oxygens [43]. The FTIR spectra of the produced glasses exhibit similar behavior (Fig. 3). A characteristic band at 806 cm^{-1} has been attributed to boroxol rings in borate glasses [32,38]. The absence of such band in the spectra measured in the present work suggests that no boroxol rings were present in the glasses studied in this work [32]. It can be concluded that the glass consists of BO_3 and BO_4 groups forming a random network [38]. Similar behavior was reported in $Pb_2O_3\text{--}B_2O_3$ glass systems [38, 44]. Furthermore, it appears that various amounts of ZnO or Ga_2O_3 doping do not affect the glass structure significantly, since the addition of ZnO or Ga_2O_3 did not cause any progressive changes in the FTIR spectra. Similar results were reported for $B_2O_3\text{--}ZnO\text{--}PbO_2$ glass with 10–30 mol % zinc addition [38]. On the other hand, it was reported that 1 and 5 wt % of Ga addition into 1393-B3 compositions caused a small shift in B–O–B bending vibrations and B–O stretching vibration in BO_4 unit. This behavior was attributed to formation of new BO_4 or BO_3 units in the network and modification of the glass structure by Ga addition [32]. The small shifts observed as the gallium content increased can indicate a short-range order rearrangement in the glass network. Similar shift was also reported for a glass in the $B_2O_3\text{--}ZnO\text{--}Na_2O\text{--}CaO\text{--}P_2O_5\text{--}Ga_2O_3$ system [31]. Further examination by ^{11}B MAS NMR revealed that the BO_4/BO_3 ratio decreased by increasing the gallium content, indicating the increase of the number of NBO in the glass network [31]. However, the small shifts of several

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of 1393-B3 powder at different magnifications.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of produced Zn and Ga doped borate glasses.

peaks observed in this study (Fig. 3) are not sufficient for understanding the effect of these ions in the glass structure, and further structural studies will be necessary.

Fig. 4 shows the results of DTA analysis of the produced glasses. The endothermic peak corresponds to glass transition (T_g), while the exothermic peaks indicate the crystallization temperatures (T_{C1} and T_{C2}) (Table 2). Fig. 4 shows typical thermal curves of the parent composition apart from the gallium-doped glasses that show two different crystallization peaks. The measured T_g and T_c for the parent composition are similar to those found in the literature [45]. Negligible changes in T_g have been observed for zinc and gallium doping. On the other hand, the addition of gallium decreased the crystallization temperature: even though gallium is known to have an intermediate role in the glass structure, it may also act as a network former which is consistent with the results reported previously [31]. Also, the changes in T_c have an impact on the glass processing window, i.e., the temperature interval between the T_g and the onset of crystallization. In this study, the addition of gallium decreased the width of glass processing window since the addition of gallium decreased the T_c , possibly by affecting the content of BO_3 units in the glass [1]. The increase in BO_4 units was found to decrease the resistance of borate glasses to crystallization [1]. The processing window is the key factor to consider for designing and producing biomaterials-like porous scaffolds and sintered samples without crystallization [1].

ICP-OES analysis was performed to verify the chemical composition of the prepared glasses. Table 3 summarizes the final composition, expressed in mol % of oxides, for glasses prepared by melting procedure. The nominal (Table 1) and the measured compositions of the glasses are matching.

3.2. In vitro bioactivity

The precipitation of calcium phosphate (Ca-P) or HA on the glass surface in contact with physiological fluids is the main property of BGs. Unlike silicate bioactive glasses, there is no silica rich layer between unreacted glass and HA precipitation in the case of borate glasses [3].

Table 2

Summary of the glass transition (T_g) and crystallization temperatures (T_{C1} and T_{C2}) of the produced glasses.

Glass Type	T_g (°C)	T_{C1} (°C)	T_{C2} (°C)
1393-B3	511	779	
1Zn	506	779	
3Zn	504	803	
6Zn	502	796	
1Ga	512	625	753
3Ga	508	616	724
6Ga	502	625	677

Table 3

Measured chemical compositions of borate bioactive glasses analyzed by ICP-OES.

Oxide (mol %)	1393-B3	1Zn	3Zn	6Zn	1Ga	3Ga	6Ga
Na ₂ O	4.9 ± 0.02	4.8 ± 0.10	4.8 ± 0.03	4.8 ± 0.16	5.7 ± 0.03	5.7 ± 0.03	5.7 ± 0.07
K ₂ O	8.1 ± 0.03	8.0 ± 0.10	8.1 ± 0.02	8.3 ± 0.23	7.3 ± 0.02	7.3 ± 0.03	7.3 ± 0.03
MgO	7.1 ± 0.04	7.5 ± 0.11	7.4 ± 0.01	7.6 ± 0.24	7.8 ± 0.04	8.0 ± 0.12	7.9 ± 0.08
CaO	23.1 ± 0.04	22.7 ± 1.49	20.0 ± 0.06	17.5 ± 0.27	20.6 ± 0.06	18.6 ± 0.24	15.8 ± 0.18
B ₂ O ₃	55.0 ± 0.07	54.2 ± 0.46	54.9 ± 0.06	53.6 ± 0.99	55.6 ± 0.09	55.0 ± 0.31	55.0 ± 0.23
P ₂ O ₅	1.8 ± 0.03	1.8 ± 0.02	1.8 ± 0.02	1.9 ± 0.03	1.9 ± 0.14	2.0 ± 0.09	2.0 ± 0.06
ZnO	–	1.7 ± 1.16	3.0 ± 0.01	6.3 ± 0.14	–	–	–
Ga ₂ O ₃	–	–	–	–	1.0 ± 0.02	3.2 ± 0.06	6.3 ± 0.22

Therefore, the bioactive response of borate glasses is faster than that of silicate BGs. SBF solution has been commonly used to evaluate the bioactivity of glasses and the formation of HA layer on the surface because it contains ionic concentrations similar to human blood plasma

Fig. 4. DTA curves of a) Zn and b) Ga doped glasses compared with the original composition.

[46]. Fig. 5 shows the surface of borate glass particles after 7 days of immersion in SBF, and Fig. 6 shows the XRD patterns of the Zn and Ga doped glasses after 1 and 7 days of immersion in SBF. XRD patterns of the doped glasses are similar to those of the parent glass. All glasses show diffraction maxima attributed to HA formation already after 1 day of immersion in SBF. However, a decrease of intensity of the HA peak (especially for the 6Zn composition) was observed after 7 days compared to 1 day incubation. A possible reason for this result could be related to the substitution of Zn^{2+} for Ca^{2+} in the HA crystals and the reduction of crystallinity [47,48]. Even if the HA content may decrease, the total amount of amorphous calcium phosphate increases. Another reason for the HA intensity decrease could be a decrease in stability of HA crystals with substitution of Zn^{2+} [49,50]. Rijt et al. [49] have also

observed the destabilizing effect of zinc when incorporated in HA crystals and the gradual dissolution of Zn-HA crystals. Formation of a layer with morphology characteristic of HA was observed on the surface of 1Zn and 1Ga glasses (Fig. 5). At higher zinc and gallium doping the amount of apatite like structures on the surface was reduced. These results are consistent with previously reported data [31,51]: the crystallization and growth of HA are inhibited due to the presence of zinc. This effect is attributed to the incorporation of zinc ions with relatively small ionic radii in the HA pre-nuclei structure distorting and creating a mismatch and preventing further HA crystal growth [51]. Further addition of gallium and zinc into borate glass resulted in complete elimination of crystalline phase formation even after 28 days immersion in SBF [30]. The inhibition effect of gallium on HA formation and

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of the different borate bioactive glasses investigated (in powder form) after 7 days immersion in SBF.

Fig. 6. XRD pattern of produced glasses a) after 1 day and b) 7 days immersion in SBF showing their bioactivity (*: formation of HA).

growth in Ca-containing solution has been also reported in the literature [52]. The effect was attributed to the increase of the onset of conversion of amorphous to crystalline HA and slower transformation kinetics with increasing Ga concentration in the solution. Also, the reduction in the growth rate of HA was observed [52]. Another reason for the delay in the formation of HA precipitation could be the increase of surface acidity in gallium doped glasses [53].

3.3. Dissolution studies

The ion-doped glasses were designed to dissolve and react appropriately in the body environment. Therefore, ion release behavior of zinc and gallium-doped borate glasses was investigated in PBS and DMEM. The time dependences of the ion release from borate glasses immersed in PBS and in DMEM are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively. Additionally, the pH value during the dissolution was measured and is reported in Fig. 9. The used medium considerably affects the ion release behavior of the glasses, and it varies also depending on the solution, pH and solution's buffering capacity [54].

In PBS medium, the 1393-B3 composition shows burst release of ions after 4 h. After 8 h the ion release decreased, which can be considered as an indicator of the early apatite formation on the glass surface. 1Zn BG shows a behavior similar to the parent glass. On the other hand, the samples with higher amount of zinc do not show any burst release of ions during the first 4 h. The reason could be that the increase of zinc content leads to a change of its role from network modifier to an intermediate oxide. It is suggested that addition of 5 mol % ZnO may reduce the number of NBO [55]. In the case of formation of tetrahedral ZnO_4^{2-} , calcium is needed to balance charges. It removes cations from the glass network and increases the number of bridging oxygens. Similar behavior has been observed also for zinc doped silicate bioactive glass systems [23,55,56]. The newly formed bonds (Si–O–Zn) have lower bond strength than Si–O–Si bonds which was confirmed by thermal analysis results [23]. Hence, the BG bioactivity decreases by the reduction of the glass dissolution. The release of alkaline earth and alkali ions decreases with increasing amount of Zn ions. This behavior can also explain the lower pH value in comparison to the parent glass (Fig. 8) [23].

Gallium doped borate glasses did not show any burst release of ions

during the first 4 h. Except for the ion release in the first 4 h of immersion, zinc and gallium doped borate glasses show similar dissolution trend to the parent glass, and the increase of the amount of zinc slightly decreased the release of ions. Since calcium showed a low release rate, the dissolution profiles of all borate glasses indicate that calcium was incorporated in the precipitation of the CaP rich layer. Boron and magnesium showed linear release kinetics after 48 h for all glass compositions. Zinc release could not be detected in PBS medium. This could be due to formation of highly insoluble compounds with zinc and phosphate such as $Zn_3(PO_4)_2$ ($K_{sp} = 9.0 \times 10^{-33}$) during formation of the calcium phosphate layer in PBS medium [45,57]. On the other hand, the concentration of gallium released reached ~ 23 mg/L from the glass with 6 mol % gallium addition after 7 days immersion in PBS. The release of gallium ions increased proportionally with the amount of gallium in the glass.

Ion release in DMEM gives different results compared to PBS. All compositions showed higher ion release compared to PBS. This was attributed to the fact that the formation of HA in cell culture medium was reduced considering that the adsorption of proteins from DMEM inhibited mineral formation. Therefore, the surface reactions of the glass were not influenced by the HA layer. These findings are in agreement with reported data in the literature: calcite formation was preferred over HA due to the presence of a high amount of calcium and carbonate in DMEM [58].

Boron showed similar ion release behavior during the first 48 h for all compositions. After 48 h, the release of boron ions slowed down and showed a decrease in the base composition. However, gallium doped borate glasses showed an increase of boron release after 48 h: 1Ga showed a decrease after 96 h, while 3Ga and 6Ga did not show any decrease in the release of boron during the immersion test. 6Zn composition showed significantly lower release of boron compared to the parent glass after 48 h, which also supports the hypothesis that zinc ions hinder ion exchange [59].

The dissolution profiles of zinc doped borate glasses showed a release of Ca and P similar to the parent glass. However, gallium doped borate glasses showed higher release of calcium for 3Ga and 6Ga borate glass compositions. This may have occurred due to the delay of HA layer formation in DMEM, so the detected amount of Ca^{2+} ions in the solution

Fig. 7. Ion dissolution profiles of zinc and gallium doped borate glasses in PBS as a function of immersion time.

Fig. 8. Ion dissolution profiles of zinc and gallium doped borate glasses in DMEM (cell culture medium) as a function of immersion time.

was higher. Depletion of P from the solution was observed up to 96 h. Afterwards, the concentration of P increased, and it was substantially higher for the 6Ga composition. The concentration of Mg also showed higher release compared with that in PBS medium, and doped borate glasses showed a similar trend with the base composition. It was possible to detect the release of zinc in DMEM medium. The amount of zinc increased in the first 48 h, and afterwards showed a decreasing trend. Gallium release showed the same trend in both tested media, but 7 times higher ion concentration was measured in DMEM after 7 days of immersion.

1393-B3 glass composition showed a linear increase of pH, reaching a maximum of 7.83 ± 0.04 in PBS. In DMEM, the pH value increased up to 96 h with a maximum pH of 8.67 ± 0.02 , before decreasing again. An exception was represented by the sample 6Zn, for which the pH

decreased already after 48 h. Gallium doping did not influence the pH values. In general, the pH was affected more in cell culture medium than in PBS.

3.4. Antibacterial efficiency

All tested BG compositions showed similar trends in terms of the inhibition of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria strains (Figs. 10 and 11). The antibacterial test results revealed significant growth inhibition during the first hours for both bacteria strains and an increasing effect with time. With respect to gallium, zinc doped glasses showed higher antibacterial effect for both tested strains. During the first 4 h of the test 1393-B3 and 1 mol % Zn doped glasses showed higher inhibitory effect than the other compositions. After 24 h, the zinc doped compositions and parent glass showed similar results against the Gram-positive bacteria strain.

Although the antibacterial effect of ZnO is widely known, the exact mechanism of inhibition or killing bacteria is still not completely understood [8]. The mechanism of the inhibitory effect of Zn has been attributed to damaging the cell membrane or the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [7,9]. In low concentrations, zinc is essential for all living systems. On the other hand, higher concentrations of zinc inhibit cellular functions. It was reported that zinc content between 10^{-5} M and 10^{-3} M could decrease sugar transport, amino acid uptake and electron transfer in bacteria [60].

Gallium addition showed lower inhibitory effect compared to Zn against Gram-positive bacteria while the effect against Gram-negative bacteria was similar. The reason could be explained considering the different cell wall structure and thickness between these two species. The cell wall of Gram-positive bacteria mainly consists of peptidoglycan while the Gram-negative bacteria cell wall is made of lipid A, lipopolysaccharide, and peptidoglycan. The results of this study confirm partly the susceptibility of *E. coli* to Ga ions. Similar results have been observed for the antibacterial efficiency of gallium nitrate against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The results showed that the minimum inhibitory concentration of gallium nitrate was 256 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for *E. coli*, and 512 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for *S. aureus*. In addition, after treatment with gallium nitrate, the cell membrane was observed to be rough, shrunk and contained features that can be interpreted as cell membrane damage: on the other hand, the cell structure of *S. aureus* remained integral. This observation suggests that *S. aureus* has much a stronger defense system against gallium [61].

The evaluation of the results obtained in this study revealed that the parent glass shows a similar effect as the doped glasses. The effect is especially pronounced after 24 h, and against Gram-negative bacteria, and was attributed to the change of pH. However, the pH of 3Ga composition was lower, which could be a reason for the slightly lower antibacterial effect of the 3Ga composition after 4 and 8 h. Borate glasses without the addition of therapeutic ions have been already reported to have antibacterial properties [62–64]. Since the amount of boron in the parent glass composition is relatively high and the dilution rate is low, the demonstration of the antibacterial effect of Zn and Ga additives is difficult. A previous study has shown that despite the fact that the zinc ratio in borate glass was kept constant, the decrease of Zn^{2+} release with time can be considered a sign of incorporation of zinc into the formed HA structure [30]. This behavior is also supported by the observation of HA formation from the first day of immersion. Another reason could be that the dissolution of bioactive glasses after 1 day is not sufficient to achieve a critical concentration of the particular ion to affect bacteria. Another scenario might be that the addition of zinc and gallium decreases the boron release from the glass, which is not compensated by the release of zinc and gallium.

Fig. 12 shows the results from the agar-disk diffusion test. In literature, an inhibition zone larger than 1 mm is considered to be associated with an antibacterial effect [65]. Hence, all borate glass compositions showed an antibacterial effect against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Only the 6Zn composition showed significant growth

Fig. 9. pH values during immersion test of Zn doped and Ga doped glasses in PBS and DMEM.

Fig. 10. Antibacterial activity of produced glasses after 4 h, 8 h, and 24 h against Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) bacteria (n = 3, *: p < 0.05, NS: p > 0.05).

Fig. 11. Antibacterial activity of produced glasses after 4 h, 8 h, and 24 h against Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria (n = 3, *: p < 0.05, NS: p > 0.05).

inhibition effect compared to the base composition. Since the idea behind this method is that the inhibition of bacteria growth is directly related to the dissolution of antimicrobial components from the disk, a lower amount of zinc addition did not show any effect on antibacterial behavior. The result is in line with the results of ion release tests and

literature data. Schuhladden et al. [65], for example, added copper (3 wt %) and zinc (1 wt%) to borate bioactive glass (1393-B3) but the slightly improved antibacterial effect of Zn was relatively minor compared to that of Cu. In the present study, at all-time points 6Ga showed

Fig. 12. Antibacterial activity of produced glasses after 1, 2 and 3 days against a) Gram-positive and b) Gram-negative bacteria.

significantly higher inhibition effect compared to the base compositions, which is in line with the results of the ion release tests.

3.5. In vitro cytotoxicity

Cell viability assays were carried out using different dilutions of the eluates (10%, 1%, 0.1% and 0.01%) after 48 h of incubation (Figs. 13 and 14). Although the bioactive glasses exhibited a concentration-dependent increase of cytotoxicity similar to results obtained by other authors [5,66], explained by static test conditions and unaltered pH values, an increment in the viability of the cells is noticeable with decreasing the dosage of the eluates. This can be suggested as a reason for the lower cell viability in comparison to the control group. For example, Balasubramanian et al. [67] conducted an indirect cell study with a similar glass composition using ST-2 cell line with 1%, 0.1% and 0.01% wt./v of bioactive glass scaffolds extracts. Similarly, high concentrations of bioactive glass were found to be toxic [67]. In this study, in the dilution of 10 % wt./v, 1Ga composition showed slightly higher cell viability compared to other compositions. This was attributed to slightly higher release of B after 24 h in both media, and especially in PBS. These findings support the idea that low concentrations of boron into cell culture medium show better cell viability and support secretion

Fig. 13. Relative viability of MG-63 cells with Zn doped glasses compared with the parent glass in different dilution rates (n = 9, samples in triplicate, *: p < 0.05, NS: p > 0.05).

Fig. 14. Relative viability of MG-63 cells with Ga doped glasses compared with the parent glass in different dilution rates (n = 9, samples in triplicate, *: p < 0.05, NS: p > 0.05).

of angiogenic growth factor, since boric acid promotes angiogenesis [67, 68]. On the other hand, it is important to note that high content of boron (>50 ppm) was found to be cytotoxic in in-vitro studies [59]. Interestingly, the addition of 1 mol % Zn and 6 mol % Ga in the parent glass composition showed similar results as the positive control group and reached 89 ± 6% and 94 ± 4% of cell viability, respectively. Previously, it has been reported that specific concentrations of zinc and gallium improved the biological performance (cell proliferation and collagen synthesis) of silicate BGs and showed therapeutic effect on osteoblastic cells [33,69].

As shown in the H&E staining images in Fig. 15, the cell density was excessive except for the negative control group. The cells exhibited their phenotypical cell morphology, and cell confluence results are in accordance with the cell viability measurements.

4. Conclusions

Zinc and gallium-doped borate bioactive glasses were successfully

Fig. 15. H&E stained MG-63 cultivated with 0.01% glass powder extracts.

produced via melt-quenching method and characterized by SEM, XRD, FTIR, and DTA. The actual glass compositions were verified by ICP-OES and matched the theoretical compositions. Precipitation of HA occurred in all produced glasses upon immersion in SBF. The dissolution behavior of the glasses was studied in PBS and DMEM media and confirmed an increased ion release in the cell culture medium. The addition of zinc decreased the ion release rates, whereas gallium increased the ion release in both media. The antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) and *E. coli* (Gram-negative) bacteria was confirmed by Broth Dilution and Agar Disk Diffusion method. 6Zn and 6Ga compositions showed significant antibacterial properties against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively. Specific concentration of Zn and Ga doped glasses extracts exhibited higher cell viability compared to 1393-B3 BG towards osteoblast-like MG-63 cells. Future work will be focused on the investigation of cell response and antibacterial properties in direct contact with the glasses. Moreover, incorporation of the glasses in composites for tissue engineering applications will be investigated.

CrediT author statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of the project Fun-Glass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566 and was also carried out in the frame of the project Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass (CEGLASS), ITMS code 313011R453, operational program Research and Innovation, co-funded from European Regional Development Fund. Financial support of this work by the grants SAS-MOST JRP 2018/02, VEGA 1/0098/19 and VEGA 1/0191/20 is gratefully acknowledged.

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